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SOCIAL FACTORS AND LANGUAGE VARIATION: EVIDENCE FROM LABOV'S MARTHA'S VINEYARD AND NEW YORK CITY STUDIES

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Abstract. *This paper summarizes two sociolinguistic studies by Labov (1963, 1972) that investigate how social factors influence language variation and change. The first study, conducted in Martha's Vineyard, examined the pronunciation of diphthongs /ai/ and /au/ and showed that local identity, economic pressure, and tourism influenced speech variation. The second study, conducted in New York City, analyzed the use of postvocalic /r/ in relation to social class and prestige using rapid anonymous surveys. The findings of both studies demonstrate that language variation is systematically linked to social structure, identity, and class rather than occurring randomly.*

Keywords: *Sociolinguistics, language variation, social factors, social class, identity, Martha's Vineyard, New York City, Labov, pronunciation change, social stratification.*

Аннотация. *В данной работе рассматриваются два социолингвистических исследования Лабова (1963, 1972), изучающие влияние социальных факторов на языковые изменения и вариативность. Первое исследование на Марта-Виньярде показало, что произношение дифтонгов /ai/ и /au/ связано с местной идентичностью, экономическим давлением и туризмом. Второе исследование в Нью-Йорке анализировало использование поствокального /r/ в зависимости от социального класса и престижа с помощью быстрых анонимных наблюдений. Результаты показывают, что языковая вариативность систематически связана с социальной структурой, идентичностью и классом.*

Ключевые слова: *Социолингвистика, языковая вариативность, социальные факторы, социальный класс, идентичность, Марта-Виньярд, Нью-Йорк, Лабов, изменение произношения, социальная стратификация.*

Introduction: Language is not only a system of communication but also a reflection of social structure. Sociolinguistics studies how language varies depending on social factors such as age, occupation, location, and class. One of the most influential researchers in this field is William Labov, who demonstrated that language change is closely connected to social meaning.

In his study on Martha's Vineyard (1963), Labov investigated how local speakers used different pronunciations of diphthongs to express identity and resistance to social and economic changes. Later, in his New York City study (1972), he examined how the pronunciation of postvocalic /r/ was influenced by social class and prestige. Together, these studies provide strong evidence that language variation is socially motivated rather than random.

Methodology. The study carried out by Labov (1963) focused on the influence of social factors like age, occupation, geographic location, attitude, and social identity on language change and the way people speak. As the site for research, Martha's Vineyard, an island in Massachusetts was chosen, because this site was "separated from the mainland by three miles", making it a suitable setting to study language variation (Labov, 1963, p. 275). The study focused on the diphthongs /ai/ and /au/ since these sounds showed noticeable variation in pronunciation among different speakers on Martha's Vineyard. This variation was influenced by social and economic factors, including poverty, the island's independence on tourism, and rising property prices, caused by wealthy summer visitors who were buying land, pushing out older residents. In response, many fishermen and older islanders in Chilmark adopted strong centralization of those diphthongs as a marker of identity. In this way, they tried to resist the changes brought by tourism and distinguish themselves from outsiders. From this research, we can find out that the increasing centralization of /ai/ and /au/ was not random, but the influence of cultural and economic pressures. Labov (1972) conducted his later study in New York City, where he investigated how the pronunciation of postvocalic /r/ changes according to social stratification, which refers to "the product of social differentiation and social evaluation" (Labov, 1972, p. 50). It means that the way people speak can show their position in society because there are certain speech patterns that are associated with higher or lower social prestige. Rather than comparing very distinct professions, like lawyers or file clerks, Labov focused on salespeople working in three department stores that varied in status: Saks (upper class), Macy's (middle class), and S. Klein (lower class). This time, as the tool of investigation, Labov used casual anonymous interactions through asking for directions rather than formal interviews. As Mather (2012) noted, anonymous surveys help "neutralize the observer's paradox" by preventing participants from modifying their answers and getting more reliable results. When responding the question "Where is the women's

shoes?” and directing customers to the “fourth floor”, salespeople at Saks, the most prestigious store, used /r/ the most, while its use was less in the middle-class store, Macy’s, and, lastly, employees at the lower-class store, S. Klein, used it at least. From the experiment, it was clear that the use of postvocalic /r/ was closely linked to social class of people. Both studies highlight the influence of social factors on language change. The study conducted in 1963 focused on regional differences in speech based on geographical location through formal interviews, while the study in 1972 explored the impact of prestige and social class on language use through rapid anonymous survey.

The list of used literature:

Labov, W. (1963). The Social Motivation of a Sound Change. *WORD*, 19(3), 273–309. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00437956.1963.11659799>

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